

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in Alpine Region (Poland)

PROBLEM

What is the most popular and frequently used agroecological method of weed control in the Alpine Region?

STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS

Among surveyed farmers from Poland's alpine region, crop rotation is the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control. It is advised by 83% of surveyed farmers. The use of certified seed is also very popular, with 75% of respondents using it. Less popular are inter-row cultivation (31%), special planting dates (28%), and competitive cultivars (28%). One-quarter of the respondents used mowing, grazing, and hand weeding. Respondents were also asked about weed control methods used by farmers in the past, but they no longer use them. Half of the respondents indicated mixed cropping. Approximately 1/5 of the respondents no longer use high planting densities. Among the methods that farmers had heard about but never used, the most common were soil cover and flame weeding (69%), interrow cultivation (64%), narrow rows (64%), and weed maps (61%).

Figure 1: Crop rotation in the Alpine bioregion. Photo by A. Synowiec

RECOMMENDATION

Properly designed crop rotation, comprising ca. 50% of cereals and a composition of winter and spring crops, is the most reliable method to keep agricultural pests, including weeds, under control. Crop rotation can also improve soil physical and chemical qualities, especially when legumes and other deeply rooted crops are included. It substantially adds to above- and below-ground biodiversity in an agricultural landscape. There is a need to research, advise, and keep farmers informed about the qualities of crop rotation to steer agriculture toward profitable and sustainable production systems.

KEYWORDS

alpine region, cereals, crop rotations, certified seed material

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